

Is Pedagogical Ethos Teachable and Learnable? The Development of a Didactic-Methodical Approach for the Practice of Ethos in Teacher Education

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Introduction

Teacher education should meet the requirement of training future teachers in the best possible way in terms of subject matter, subject didactics, and pedagogy. The pedagogical profession also demands that attitudes be addressed and conveyed in the context of the tasks and functions of education and society. However, within the context of fields of action in schools, areas of tension and sometimes also of contradiction appear that cannot or be solved satisfactorily by pedagogical action. In this context, Helsper speaks of antinomies, referring to the structures of the school field that are always co-determining or shaping the pedagogical actions of teachers (cf. Helsper, 1996). Therefore teachers (and this includes experienced as well as prospective teachers) are required to take responsibility in challenging school situations based on general moral maxims and to make their own decisions, which should always have the well-being of their students and the best possible learning support as a goal. In situations with an open outcome, therefore, action must be taken individually on the basis of one's own pedagogical ethos. Pedagogical ethos requires the assumption of responsibility for the learning, education, and development of children and adolescents within the framework of a socially legitimized mission and, at the same time, the assumption of personal responsibility for the consequences of actions within one's own sphere of influence (cf. Oser, 2018). Ethos refers to attitudes in regard to one's own principles and how they shape one's actions: ethos involves one's own individual moral decision-making capacity.

1. *The Process of Creating a Manual for Teacher Education*

The project, which focused on the topic of pedagogical ethos in teacher education, was called ELBE, "Ethos in the Teaching Profession" (ELBE). This resulted in a "Handbook for Practicing a Professional Attitude." The project focused on the connection between fundamental questions of pedagogical ethos and the practicing of ethos in the sense of professionalization. The team of researchers focused on the question "Is pedagogical ethos learnable?" and then, as a consequence, "Is pedagogical ethos teachable in teacher training?" The goal of the work of the 10 researchers—all of them professionals in the field of teacher training—was to create a manual, the ELBE-Manual, to introduce pedagogical ethos as practicing moral decision-making skills in university teacher training. In a research process lasting several years, the German-Austrian research team designed a manual (Rödel, Schauer, Christof, Agostini, Brinkmann, Pham Xuan, Schratz, & Schwarz, 2022) for practicing moral decision-making skills. They engaged in an intensive process of studying the history and current debates surrounding the topic of pedagogical ethos. Milestones in their own theories of pedagogical ethos for teacher education were drafted, in which reference

was also made to current professional theories (cf. Oser et al., 2021, *The International Handbook on Teacher Ethos*, and Schratz et al., 2008, The EPIK Model).

The manual has been designed for application in the field of teacher education, and its intention is to help prospective teachers become familiar with the topic of responsibility and pedagogical ethos within the context of their teaching actions. The manual was designed for practical use in university courses in the field of teacher training. It consists of 24 examples of pedagogical practice. The team of researchers analyzed practical experiences drawn from portfolios of student teachers using the method of document analysis (cf. Hoffmann, 2018). The examples were taken from internship reports of student teachers at the University of Innsbruck and are thus documents reporting lived experience of everyday teaching. They tell of difficulties, ambiguities, and challenges, but also of experiences of successful and “fruitful” moments.

Following the theory work, the team designed a didactic approach for practicing moral decision-making in order to develop pedagogical ethos. The didactical model consists of two bigger parts. The whole process always takes examples from lived experience as its starting points. Firstly, there is a three-step process, in which ethos as a moral decision-making ability, in the sense of Aristotelian *phronesis*, is practiced. The three-step process is composed of (1) looking for individual interpretations and experiences in the context of the example; (2) explaining one’s own positions and personal reasons; (3) expressing irritation regarding the situation and responses and establishing distance from possible interpretations.¹ In the second part—called the a-b-c scheme—the ambivalences and ambiguities shown in the examples are discussed, and the ethical premises are taken into account. Firstly, the ‘appropriateness’ of a situational, practical experience of action can only be thematized, assessed and judged in retrospect and, secondly, this ‘appropriateness’ does not consist of acting according to normative guidelines within fixed limits, but of perceiving the particularity of a situation and thus responding and acting in the sense of moral decision-making. Going through this process, (future) teachers get an idea of—and also get in touch with—their pedagogical ethos.

In an empirical phase, the ELBE manual was used in 15 university seminars at three locations—Berlin, Vienna, and Innsbruck—to design seminar sessions, and the testing was accompanied by a survey of the lecturers.

2. Theoretical Background

Why is ethos, or more specifically pedagogical ethos, a topic in teacher training? Teacher education should meet the requirement of training future teachers in the best possible way in terms of their subject, but also in terms of didactics and pedagogy. The pedagogical profession also demands that teachers develop appropriate attitudes, because they have to assume important tasks and functions in society, such as socializing, educating, and forming the next generation. A large number of competency models in teacher education are limited to skills and abilities that professional teachers acquire due to their functions in the school field (cf. EPIK, Schratz & Schrittmesser, 2011, INTASC Standards, COACTIV, Oser 88 Standards, Standards der KMK, ...).

¹ Irritation refers here to a sense of unease linked to the recognition of ambiguity, uncertainty, or discomfort generated by the depicted situation, while distancing refers to a stepping back from the situation and positioning oneself, recognizing and acknowledging its bothersome aspects. These irritations and the distancing can be triggered by the situation itself, by discussion led by students, or by reflection on questions explicitly introduced by teachers.

In the COACTV model by Baumert and Kuntner (2011), reference is made to values and beliefs, which also have an influence on teachers' actions. The formula for the professional action of teachers could therefore be stated as follows: Values and beliefs, as well as knowledge and skills, together result in the professional competence of teachers.

However, since pedagogical action cannot be standardized and there is no technology relating to how to act in the classroom (cf. the "technology deficit of education," Luhmann, 1996), the question remains open as to what teachers refer to when making everyday decisions, what ultimately justifies their actions. Competency models and mission statements in teacher education provide standards and normative frameworks for how professional teachers should act, but not for how they should ultimately make their very concrete decisions in a challenging school situation. Professional teacher action is clearly different from non-professional action in a pedagogical situation because teachers do not act in their function from a personal, private perspective, but within the framework of their function, their public mission, which they have to fulfill in the institution of the school. On the one hand, this public mission is framed by rules, structures and norms concerning the school field; on the other hand, it consists of a pedagogical ethos, a moral obligation, which is oriented towards the norms of society and towards one's own moral principles. Pedagogical ethos means taking responsibility for the learning, education, and development of children and adolescents within the framework of a socially legitimized mission and, at the same time, taking personal responsibility for the consequences of actions within one's own sphere of influence (cf. Oser, 2018). Ethos means attitude in the sense of one's own principles that shape one's actions—ethos as one's own individual moral decision-making capacity. When these fundamental principles are related to one's own professional pedagogical actions, this forms a teacher's own pedagogical ethos. However, a teacher's own pedagogical ethos cannot be articulated per se; it exists as a personal principle, but only becomes visible when an immediately unresolvable conflict, a dilemma, a kind of crisis in action, arises that demands a decision and an action. Teachers are often called upon to make a decision and to strike a balance between justice, caring, and truthfulness (cf. Oser, 2018). Ethos as an implicit and situation-bound professional and experiential action cannot be learned or practiced in teacher education, but the moral decision-making ability that manifests itself in an attitude can be trained. In situations with an open outcome, therefore, action must be taken individually on the basis of one's own pedagogical ethos.

What is ethos and, more specifically, pedagogical ethos? Ethos is understood as a sum of values, as a value attitude, or as a responsible attitude. The ethos of teachers can be defined as values and value orientations in professional action. Values and value orientations are standards of orientation and guiding principles by which individuals and groups are guided in their choice of action. One's own pedagogical ethos shows itself in difficult school situations as successful practice, which is based on the moral decision-making ability of a person. In this context, moral decision-making means being aware of one's own judgment patterns, which enables the possibility of alternative judgements as well. For this judgment, it is important to consider what is "right" or "responsible" as an ethical action in a school or classroom setting. This cannot be determined solely by laws or by universal norms and values. We assume that the complexity of moral decisions in a sphere of inter-bodily connection with other actors in pedagogical situations manifests itself as positionings. Positionings represent pre-reflective forms of action and behavior towards certain situations, individuals, or challenges, which are, however, mostly implicitly structured and can only be made explicit in retrospect. Therefore, it can only be decided in retrospect whether a certain situation

involved a form of successful practice and whether professional actions took place. But is pedagogical ethos learnable and, as a consequence, is it then teachable in teacher education?

The thesis in this project was, Ethos cannot be taught in the sense of instruction, but must be trained for and practiced as a moral decision-making ability founded on the basis of a particular example. Therefore, there is a focus on the questions, How does a (prospective) teacher position him/herself in practice on the basis of ethical values and professional experience? How does the (prospective) teacher take up a position with regard to the subject matter and the students and thereby assume pedagogical responsibility?

Based on this thesis that pedagogical ethos cannot be learned or taught, some principles regarding how it is possible to practice pedagogical ethos with students were developed. The practice of pedagogical ethos can be supported with certain steps. These steps comprise finding and justifying different readings of a situation, experiencing phases of irritation and distancing, and recognizing and considering alternative possibilities for action. Another goal is to sensitize teachers to the ambiguities in these practical situations and to practice a reflective approach to the need to make decisions and take responsibility as a teacher, even in ambivalent situations.

3. The Didactical Setting to Develop Pedagogical Ethos

Ethos shows itself as successful practice in which a person positions him/herself or takes a stand and assumes responsibility, on the basis of his or her evaluation and professional experiences. Ethos emerges only in practical situations and in the experience of the situations. Ethos is based on a moral decision-making capacity. This can only be practiced, but not taught in the sense of instruction or didactically guided competence building.

Therefore, a didactical setting was developed in order to practice moral decision-making. The goal of this program is to develop the moral decision-making ability and judgment formation of prospective teachers. The basis of this approach is that ethos in the above sense, as an implicit and situation-bound professional and experience-related action, cannot—strictly speaking—be practiced, but that the moral decision-making ability in the sense of an ethos can be trained. The process is started with short examples from real practices. The examples, as mentioned before, were taken from the internship reports of student teachers at the University of Innsbruck. They are therefore documents reporting lived experience from pedagogical practice.

The three-step process starts (1) with the collection of different ways of reading the presented example. Later, the steps are illustrated with an example. In a next step (2), students are asked to position themselves and justify their attitude. This is followed (3) by a deliberate creation of irritation, such as by taking another position in this situation. Additionally, new alternatives of ways to act can be collected by the students. This is the three-step process “collect-position-irritate.”

The next phase of the process addresses the ambiguities of the situation in the example. An example of the ambiguities in a specific practical situation will be given later.

The last step of this setting—called the a-b-c scheme—also consists of three parts. First (a), a question is asked about ethos as situated action and as successful practice in the example. Then

(b), the prospective teachers (the students) look for ethos expressed as an attitude within the context of responsibility. Finally (c), the teacher students' views of ethos as a bodily, resistant statement based on profession-specific and professional experience are gathered.

Now, we will briefly explain why we use examples as a starting point in practicing pedagogical ethos. Günther Buck pinpoints the value of having a specific example. He states that the example “presents a particular with the invitation to consider it from the point of view of the general” (Buck, 1989, p. 98). In the example, the “presentation of a general in the particular” (Lippitz, 1987, p. 116) can be seen. In this case, all the examples are school situations; they have “field character” and show the material quality and concreteness of the specific field which is presented by the example. An example illustrates the intersubjective and thus relational experiences which can be recognized by others more easily. The meaning of an example is not revealed as a rule that can be objectified, but arises in intuitive comprehension.

The aim is to enable student teachers to reflect on and learn from their own subjective experiences, which play a crucial role in shaping their understanding of ethical decision-making within the teaching profession. By analyzing a concrete situation, a multitude of phenomena of the same or an analogous nature can be discovered through reflection and further thinking. Because future situations also belong to the field of the school, they follow the same principles. In working with examples, student teachers precisely gain a recognitional vision of the concrete that contains the possibility of (future) cognition regarding a multitude of phenomena of the same or an analogous nature, obeying the same principles (cf. Buck, 1989, p. 40).

4. An Example of Didactic Implementation

To show how this didactic procedure involving the three-step process works, we will now focus on an example from the manual of the ELBE research group. This example was written by a student during the course of reflecting on the whole teacher education process. This situation seemed to be important enough for him/her to discuss it:

The students seemed to be relatively restless during this lesson, and I had already admonished them once, telling them to be quieter and pay attention. This only lasted for a few minutes and the noise level in the class rose again. I knew this class better by this point and this commotion puzzled me, so I simply asked what was going on today. One student explained to me that two hours ago the math test had taken place and therefore they just couldn't concentrate properly. Then I decided to postpone the—admittedly rather dry—grammar topic until the next lesson and instead play a turn of “Vocabulary King” with them. I had done this exercise with them a few lessons before, and it seemed to me that they had a lot of fun doing it, but they still took it seriously and engaged with English. This seemed like a good compromise for me. (cf. Rödel, Schauer, Christof, Agostini, Brinkmann, Pham Xuan, Schratz, & Schwarz, 2022, p. 50)

It is important to have a look at this example. This situation seems to be one that could happen very often (as mentioned before, cf. Buck, 1989). Yet for the student who wrote this example, it was special; because this procedure had not been planned to be like this, the student teacher was irritated, and the situation remained in his or her mind. He or she asked himself/herself if he/she

was acting right from a professional perspective, if this was a successful practice. In this school situation, you can feel the character of the school field, too. It is not simply like an interview. When someone talks about an incident, here the quality of the material is much higher and more concrete (Lippitz, 1984, p. 16), so that everyone knows what is going on. This experience could be recognized by others in this classroom, and everyone who is a participant in the field of schools can comprehend and talk about this illustration.

An example like this can be part of a seminar for teaching pedagogical ethos because it can provide a starting point for talking about subjective (pre-)experience. In addition to subjective experiences, the examination of one's own subjective theories is also relevant to the discussion of pedagogical ethos and the understanding of school situations. Subjective theories have an action-guiding and action-controlling function (cf. Dann, 1989). They influence the professional actions of teachers (cf. Baumert & Kunter, 2006), and consequently have a significant influence on the planning and implementation of lessons. In addition, they already have an influence on the actions and analysis of the actions of prospective teachers—and so on their own positioning, too. Therefore, to develop one's own professional action and moral decision-making ability, it is necessary to start with an examination of one's own values, one's own subjective theories or beliefs, so as to understand one's own and other perspectives and to discuss them in the context of professionalization.

By analyzing this concrete situation, a multitude of phenomena of the same or an analogous nature can be discovered through reflection and further thinking (cf. Buck, 1989, p. 40). This will be elaborated and illustrated in the next section.

5. *The Three-step Process: “Collect—Position—Irritate”*

Building on the ELBE project, a small team of university lecturers designed a whole course with six or seven units at three universities in Vienna and Innsbruck. Four lecturers held their entire courses using this didactical procedure in master courses and bachelor courses in teacher education. Some other lecturers included this procedure in their own seminars in just one slot. We stayed in contact with the lecturers, and they collected a considerable amount of feedback from the students involved in these courses. In this way, initial experiences with the didactic approach and the manual were gained. A detailed presentation of the results can be found in Schauer, Christof & Rödel (in press).

The first step in every seminar session dealing with practicing moral decision-making skills is that the students have to read a selected school situation from the ELBE manual. The meaning of an example is not presented as a rule that can be objectified, but arises as intuitive comprehension. It is very important to collect these different ways of reading, in order to understand the situation holistically. This is possible by asking questions like these:

- How do you feel about the situation?
- What comes to your mind?
- Did you have similar experiences?
- Why do you think they act this way in this situation?

It is also possible to talk about similar experiences, or the way anybody would act in such a specific situation. To get a general overview of the situation and not just an individual opinion, it is important to include the subjective thoughts of all individual students. This viewing from the multiple perspectives of the other students is important because it makes it possible to always examine each example from new, previously unknown perspectives and viewpoints. Thus, on the one hand, questions and considerations can be formulated as experience-based and approached from one's own perspective. On the other hand, the plurality of different perspectives is revealed as offering possible and perhaps desirable oppositions for a deeper examination of the underlying realities of a particular school situation (cf. Rödel, Schauer, Christof, Agostini, Brinkmann, Pham Xuan, Schratz, & Schwarz, 2022).

In the next step in this process, the students are asked to position themselves within the context of the example and to justify their position. If we only ask them for reflections, there is nothing fixed. So there are some more questions to discuss:

- What exactly is the “compromise” referred to in the example? How do you judge the compromise?
- Why do you think the teacher/the student teacher is doing the right or wrong thing? How do you explain your conclusions?
- Why do you think your explanation is more correct than those of your colleagues? Defend your explanation in front of the others!
- On which theories or general explanations is your statement—and maybe the explanation of the others—based?
- When you compare your own view with those of your colleagues, where is there consensus and where not, and are there any completely new perspectives?

It is important to position oneself in order to realize one's own subjective theories, one's individual thinking, and also to understand the mental position in the group. It explains how people act or how they would like to act. Moreover, it makes it possible to reflect upon one's own beliefs and pedagogical attitudes.

After reflecting on beliefs and pedagogical attitudes, the next step is to provoke irritation. The purpose of triggering targeted irritation is to create a pause and to distance oneself from the situation. In this way, one's own routines can be questioned. Phenomenological practices, such as bracketing (as a return to judgment—cf. Husserl, 1939), stopping, and interrupting (both seen as a return to experience—cf. Heidegger, 1927, 1949) are significant to this process. Bracketing and thus referring back to judgments (cf. Husserl, 1939) means refraining from making definitive statements and (provisional) judgments about a particular issue, temporarily postponing judgment, as if placing the issue in parenthesis. It is neither a judgment nor a non-judgment (cf. Brinkmann, 2021, p. 40). Stopping (cf. Heidegger, 1927, 1949) or distancing oneself from a situation allows for more time to reflect on the experience (Brinkmann, 2021b, p. 44), making space for new considerations, thoughts, and the acceptance, perception, and exploration of new ideas. This approach interrupts the usual and normal, as well as familiar routines in one's actions and thinking (cf. Waldenfels, 2007). In this way, familiar orders can be disrupted, allowing new thoughts to arise and to be recognized for their otherness. So, bracketing involves first consciously

experiencing and thematizing one's own experiences. This is achieved in the work with examples by collecting one's own perspectives and interpretations. Stopping (as a return to experience—cf. Heidegger, 1927, 1949) occurs when topics or ways of acting are further questioned with additional reflective questions. In interrupting (as stepping back from what is approaching—cf. Waldenfels, 2007), when the research group is triggered by irritations, the participants try to create new perspectives. Thus, one's own actions and arguments are questioned, leading to the emergence of new ways of thinking. The goal is to provoke irritation, promote distancing and encourage reflection, ultimately with the aim to embrace unknown and tacit knowledge, enabling it to be accepted, perceived, seen and felt. In this way, familiar orders can be disrupted and strangeness can be reflected as otherness. This process enables one to “reflexively orient one's own experiences in the horizon of foreignness to other knowledge” (Brinkmann, 2021, p. 190).

The next part of the three-step process demands a positioning of the students in relation to the actions described in the given situation by discussing following questions:

- Take the position of a person standing outside who is only observing the situation, for example another teacher. How does the situation appear to them? Does this other view change your opinion?
- In the description of the scene, we cut the last part; it actually ends like this: “...This seemed like a good compromise to me, *and I had the feeling that it was also very well received by the class.*” If you know this, then how do you evaluate the action, now that you know that the last-minute change of plans “worked”? What exactly “worked” here? Is it “working” from the point of view of the class or from that of individual students?
- Imagine that in the next lesson, a large number of students demand to play the substituted game again. This creates a conflict in the class: a few students say they would rather do a grammar unit because there is a test coming up and they still need to catch up. How would you act in the trainer's place and how would you justify your actions to the students?

First of all, when the students talk about the reactions, everything seems to be clear. Perhaps, at first, the reactions of the teacher, or the thinking we are talking about, seems to be a professional act. But now everything might be different again and not everything would seem to be perfect. This is important for reflection. With this irritating factor included the students have to think about their decisions again, and maybe they reverse them. With this additional loop they develop a distance from the situation and from their own decisions. This step is really important for practicing the moral decision-making ability, and the process of making these decisions shows one's own pedagogical ethos.

5. *Ambiguities of the Situation Described*

The next step is to find ambiguities in the situation, in order to deepen one's own awareness of issues. Each example from the manual (cf. Rödel, Schauer, Christof, Agostini, Brinkmann, Pham Xuan, Schratz, & Schwarz, 2022) contains ambiguities of interpretation and positioning and thus challenges the students to take a stance on the situation described in the example and to engage in

discursive discussion with their colleagues. These school situations show conflicts or ambiguities. Ambiguity is a characteristic of practical situations in which positioning is needed. Implementing the different ambiguities in processing the situations can result in different perspectives on professional practice. Thus a professional approach to one's own actions can be discussed. Ethos means responding to this ambiguity with a moral decision-making capacity that is situationally, emotionally, and bodily grounded (cf. Rödel, Schauer, Brinkmann, & Schratz, 2022, p. 171). Accordingly, in this context, moral decision-making ability is grounded in a morality that claims to be universally binding. Otherwise such morality would lack any general binding force.

In this framework, these obligations refer to the responsibilities within the school community and thus to the rules and norms of the educational and schooling system. Building on these considerations and reflections, ambiguities in the examples are identified through the intensive examination of readings, positionings and irritations (three-step). These ambiguities are then discussed with reference to professionalization theories, incorporating the topics addressed in the examples. The focus lies on various areas of tension that are revealed in the examples. These ethical ambiguities are to be deepened in the context of "Ethos in the Teaching Profession." For this purpose, the teachers' decisions discussed in the example are collected, the ethical positioning of these decisions discussed, and the assumptions of responsibility by the persons involved in the example are shown. In addition, the different areas of tension will be illuminated with the help of theoretical references and theoretical literature, which can reinforce positions, but can also cause irritation (cf. Rödel, Schauer, Brinkmann, & Schratz, 2022, p. 173).

In relation to the above situation, the following ambiguities are dealt with by the students:

- Ambiguity 1: Responding vs. not responding (opening vs. not opening).
- Ambiguity 2: Direct control vs. indirect control / direct exercise of power vs. indirect exercise of power / open vs. veiled hierarchies.
- Ambiguity 3: Relationship to the students vs. educational mission.
- Ambiguity 4: The individual vs. the group / inequality vs. equality.

If we focus, for example, on Ambiguity 1) Responding vs. not responding (opening vs. not opening), we have to concentrate on the following passage: "One student explained to me that two hours ago the math test took place and therefore they just couldn't concentrate properly. Then I decided to postpone the—admittedly rather dry—grammar topic until the next lesson and instead play a turn of 'Vocabulary King' with them." To interpret this: the prospective teacher shows empathy in this situation regarding the restlessness of the students and does not simply ignore it and continue with the topic. The student teacher decides to discard the lesson plan and respond to the students by choosing a task that is more fun. The teacher takes a risk that this will cause them to "lag behind" in the material (cf. Rödel, Schauer, Christof, Agostini, Brinkmann, Pham Xuan, Schratz, & Schwarz, 2022). Each example contains ambiguities of interpretation and positioning, and thus challenges the students to take a stance on the situation described in the example, to participate in discursive discussion and engage with the stances of their colleagues. After the students talk about their reflections on the ambiguities, the next step is to talk about the meaning of these reflections for professionalization too. We can only notice if a teaching reaction is professional after finishing a situation and reflecting upon it.

7. A Model of Teacher Professionalization—EPIK

Another task of the didactic framework is to discuss these ambiguities from the perspective of teacher professionalization. For this purpose, we use a specific model of teacher professionalization, the EPIK model. The EPIK model originates from teacher and school research and was developed by Michael Schratz et al. (2008) at the University of Innsbruck, among others. EPIK is an acronym for *Entwicklung von Professionalität im internationalen Kontext* (“development of (teacher) professionalism in an international context,” Nairz-Wirth, 2011, p. 167). The domain approach of EPIK (cf. Paseka, Schratz & Schritteser, 2011) assumes that the professional action of teachers in school events is manifested in the interaction of the multiple facets of the decisions made in each lesson, depending on the grade level, subject, and type of school. This should also be taken into account when processing the situations from the manual. In order to prepare future teachers for these nuanced requirements in teaching, the necessary competencies in professional action are localized on the level of superordinate cross-sectional topics in the scientific debate and summarized in competency fields, called “domains” in the EPIK approach (cf. Schratz et al., 2008). Thus, this is a normative model with a view to establishing successful action as a professional teacher, and is suitable for a reflexive examination of school situations. The domains are defined as follows:

- REFLECTION AND DISCOURSE means having a critical approach to one[s own actions, recognizing the nature of a specific situation, developing self-observation strategies, recognizing general truths in specific situations, developing a larger repertoire of choices, and drawing conclusions.
- PROFESSIONAL AWARENESS means being aware of one’s own expertise in a specific subject, realizing the freedom of being a teacher and setting oneself boundaries.
- PERSONAL MASTERY means the power of individual prowess, having one’s own vision, knowing what to do and how to do it at the right time, being able to say why one is doing something and finding one’s own way to handle things.
- COLLEGIALITY means intensifying the form of dialogue, seeing oneself as a member of a professional learning community, being socially competent and open-minded.
- ABILITY TO DIFFERENTIATE mean recognizing pupils’ different learning needs, striving to develop individual learning strategies and having the knowledge and skills to deal with these differences.

In the model of Schratz et al. (2008), professionalism is considered as an expression of professional action. Professionalism in this model refers to professional action. On the one hand, it refers to the further development of the profession in the social context; on the other hand, it refers to the promotion of professional action by individuals (Paseka et al., 2011, p. 8). The EPIK concept of Schratz et al. (2008) seeks to be understood as a heuristic model to make teachers’ actions systematically visible in the context of professionalization (Schritteser, 2011, p. 112).

Schratz et al.’s (2008) theoretical framework not only includes the five domains, but also refers to the contradictions and tensions within situations. Both the actors and the situation itself are addressed. Thus, considerations for successful practice are very complex and overlap between the

given domains. Therefore, these domains of professionalization are interconnected in many ways (Schrittesser, 2011, p. 110).

The task of the trainee teachers is to discuss the common considerations in the context of professionalization, after an intensive examination of a school situation. For this purpose, the positioning and the alternatives for action mentioned are reflected upon once more with regard to the five domains.

Figure 1: EPIK Model (cf. Schratz et al., 2008)

Again, reflective questions will be integrated into the seminar:

- How do the EPIK domains show up in the positioning/alternative actions?
- What normative considerations arise for action?
- What needs to be considered in terms of domain XY for the situation described?
- Is a professional approach to the situation, in relation to all EPIK domains, evident?

Answers to these reflexive questions are intended to facilitate a profession-specific professional exchange for consideration of future courses of action.

8. Merging Pedagogical Ethos and Teacher Professionalization

Let us now examine the ambiguities arising from the example, and the arguments based on the theory of professionalization described above. This should explain why a professional teacher

would decide for one or the other variant. There are two important elements to practicing ethos in teacher education. First, it is essential to have a theory and a knowledge of pedagogical ethos in order to understand the concept and the topic. Only when the topic itself becomes clear do considerations and exercises about it become understandable. With regard to the second part, namely teacher action and professionalization, it is not enough just to think about pedagogical ethics and practice decision-making skills. It is also important to think about these considerations and the resulting action strategies from the perspective of professionalization.

To return to the situation mentioned before: is it professional to postpone the planned content of a lesson and instead play a game based on students' reactions? In the context of the discussed professionalization model, the domain "reflective and discursive ability" is evident here. In the sense of a reflexive approach, the teacher has reacted empathically, reflected on the actions, and adapted the pedagogical action. However, with regard to the domain "professional awareness," the teacher is also aware of the task of imparting knowledge and making progress with the learning material. The teacher's decision and reaction to this discrepancy relate, one, to the area of Personal Mastery and, two, to his/her own moral attitudes and values. The student teachers' task is to find and discuss these different approaches to professional action in relation to the school situations. Thus, in dealing with the perceived ambiguities, first off, one's own actions, values and moral decision-making ability are to be addressed and, in a further step, these pedagogical actions and arguments are to be analyzed in the context of professionalization in the seminar. Skills such as concentration, error tolerance and ambiguity tolerance, and judgment, and critical faculties, as well as social and moral skills such as empathy, or attitudes such as composure, are all acquired primarily through practice (cf. Rödel, Schauer, Brinkmann, & Schratz, 2022).

9. Student Feedback to This Didactic Approach

The student teachers experienced this practice when dealing with many different school situations by working through them with the three-step process (and additionally the a-b-c scheme) mentioned above. Feedback was obtained from lecturers and, in particular, from students, on whom we want to focus here. In the following, the students' experiences with the topic of "pedagogical ethos" and the related didactic approach are presented. They reported that an "exercise effect" occurred after going through several examples with the same schemes as shown before. Regular use of the same didactic procedure meant a certain security for students in analyzing and finding alternative action considerations. Thus, for the effective practice of a moral decision-making ability, the repetition of the methodological-didactic work with the students was beneficial, and a greater variety of methods would, in their view, have been counterproductive in this case.

Furthermore, well-chosen school situations were also partly responsible for the success of practicing moral decision-making skills. The students were able to connect the given examples very well with their own experiences (as students or teachers), since all examples contained certain aspects which are "very typical" for the school setting. Therefore, for the implementation of pedagogical ethos in teacher education, it is important either to use appropriate school situations (as presented in the manual), or to include the practical experiences and problematic situations which the students themselves have to deal with in their everyday school life. In any case, the students praise the very "practical" and "hands-on" parts of the university didactic implementation.

They also really like to bring in their own examples and to discuss them with others in the seminar, because they recognize the relevance of this topic for their own teaching.

However, students initially had difficulty connecting to the school situations from the manual, because some situations did not include a great deal of contextual information, such as the age of the students discussed in the example, or what happened before the situation. Some of the situations intentionally reveal less contextual information so that different perspectives on the situation can be discussed. However, the students commented that it is this contextual information that is perceived to be missing in the examples that is needed before the latter can be productively applied by students and lecturers.

To give some insight into student feedback, here is an excerpt from a final paper:

The most exciting thing for me was to solve my own slipper problem [i.e., a problem pertaining to the dress code]. As trivial as it sounds and [as] insignificant as the situation seems, the question of ethos becomes more important (it doesn't have to be a matter of life or death). Above all, I was concerned about the situation as a pupil, and I could not have said is it the pupil's fault or the teacher's fault. Now I can think about the situation in a completely different and more holistic way, which is a great gain, as many problems in everyday school life will be of this kind (slippers, mobile phones, eating in class, using the toilet, etc...). The examples of the seminar were very wisely chosen according to practical aspects. It is also interesting to reflect on the emotion that arose in part during the discussion, which alone helps to remind oneself from time to time in everyday school life that it is possible to think more clearly with a cool head. (Master course in teacher education studies at the University of Music and Performing Arts Vienna, 2022)

The extent to which the didactic approach of the ELBE manual affects students and their pedagogical ethos are explored in greater depth in the follow-up project PETAL (Pedagogical Ethos of Trainee Teachers, Schauer, 2024).

Conclusion

The feedback from most students who have attended one or more sessions on the concept of pedagogical ethos has shown that they have engaged very deeply with the examples and have been able to take away some ideas, insights, and knowledge for themselves. Beyond the knowledge and skills that can be taught in teacher education, student teachers have many questions and problems that confront them with challenging situations. These situations often come with many fears of possibly doing the wrong thing in a difficult situation. Students have also come to realize that there are no universally binding values, no universal rules and recipes for crisis situations that they can refer to in the future. What is 'right' or 'responsible' as an ethical action in a school or classroom context cannot be justified by laws or universal norms and values. Any statement made in a situation may be justified by the agent's own convictions—but it may also be otherwise, depending on judgment and justification. Ethical action in pedagogical situations cannot be clearly determined and therefore cannot be taught in teacher education (Haupt et al., 2021). What teacher training can do, however, is to address this issue in education, to help one reflect on one's own

beliefs, convictions, and attitudes—one's own pedagogical ethos—and to evaluate it with the help of theoretical approaches. To this end, it is necessary to create opportunities and frameworks in teacher education and to establish appropriate forms for teacher students to practice moral decision-making skills. Ultimately, the work presented here, with examples in the form of case studies, represents an approach that needs to be explored through further research.

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